

NATURE OF CLAY MINERALS PRESENT IN SAKRAND SOIL

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The chemical composition and electrochemical and viscous properties attribute a predominantly illitic nature to the Sakrand clay.

The properties of the subfractions of the entire clay fraction isolated from a saline soil from Sakrand (Sind) have been dealt with in a previous publication (Chatterjee and Gupta, *Science & Culture*, 1946-47, 12, 57). The present note records the results of chemical, electrochemical, viscous and mineralogical studies of the Sakrand clay. This work was undertaken to obtain information on the nature of clay minerals (*i. e.*, secondary aluminosilicate minerals) present in a saline soil and also to supplement the data already obtained, since it has been proved beyond doubt that there is not a single soil property which is not directly or indirectly connected with the nature and amounts of clay minerals present in it (Joffe, "Pedology", 1949). The clay fraction, separated according to the International method, was converted into hydrogen clay (H-clay) by repeated leaching with 0.03N hydrochloric acid, followed by washing with water and was finally dispersed in distilled water.

Chemical Composition.—The percentages of SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 , MgO and K_2O of the H-clay determined by fusion analysis are 55.10, 23.1, 11.28, 3.50 and 6.60 respectively. The H-clay did not seem to contain any measurable amount of calcium. The presence of the high amount of potassium suggests that the mineral constituent of the Sakrand clay belongs to the illite (hydrated mica) group. The general formula

with y varying from 1.0 to 1.5, has been suggested (Grim *et al.*, *Amer. Min.*, 1937, 22, 813) for minerals of this group. The amount of illite in the Sakrand clay comes to over 90% when the analytical data are fitted in the above formula. The presence of unweathered potassium bearing primary minerals, *e.g.*, feldspar, in the Sakrand clay is, however, not altogether improbable. In that case, the percentage of illite will diminish correspondingly.

Electrochemical Properties.—The potentiometric titration curve (Fig. 1) with NaOH of the H-clay, prepared from the Sakrand soil, shows a sharp inflexion at pH 7.9 and a very weak one at pH 9.3 and in this respect it is somewhat similar to those of H-kaolinite. The resemblance is, however, superficial. As for instance, the base exchange capacities (b.e.c.) calculated at the two inflexion points (*viz.* 20.0 and 52.0 milliequivalents per 100 g.) are considerably higher than the corresponding values for kaolinites (Mukherjee

and Mitra, *Nature*, 1944, 154, 821). Further, the ratio of the b. e. c' s at the first and second inflexion points in the titration curve of the Sakrand clay is 2.6, while the corresponding value for H-kaolinite is 2.0.

Viscous Property.—Apart from a slight initial decrease, the viscosity of 0.55% suspensions of the H-clay, prepared from the Sakrand soil, does not appear to change on the addition of increasing amounts of NaOH (Fig. 1). This observation indicates the absence of a marked amount of montmorillonite in this clay (Mukherjee and Mitra, *loc. cit.*). The viscosity-alkali concentration curve appears to be characteristic of illite (Indra and Neogy, unpublished) or of kaolinite (Mukherjee and Mitra, *J. Coll. Sci.*, 1946, 1, 141) The nature of the potentiometric curve and high value of the b. e. c., however, suggest the absence of marked amounts of kaolinite in this clay.

FIG. 1

Mineralogical Studies.—The percentages of heavy and light minerals present in the fine and coarse sand fractions have been determined to gain information, if possible, on the genesis and development of the Sakrand soil. The light and heavy fractions were separated by means of bromoform using a hand centrifuge. These fractions were then examined under a petrographic microscope. The results have been summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

	Light fraction.	Heavy fraction.
Coarse sand	83.5% by weight (plagioclase* and shells)	6.5% by weight (biotite*, shells and magnetite)
Fine sand	93.0% by weight [plagioclase*, quartz (few) and microcline]	7.0% by weight (biotite, 50% hornblende, 25% rest**, 25%)

* Dominant mineral.

** Rest denotes tourmaline, garnet, muscovite, zoisite, calcite and epidote.

The occurrence of the micaceous minerals in the sand fractions is in conformity with the predominantly illitic nature of the Sakrand clay. The presence of plagioclase, biotite and hornblende in large amounts indicates that weathering has not proceeded to any great extent in this soil. The very low percentage of quartz and of the alteration products of biotite and hornblende also point to the immature nature of the soil. The results of petrographic analysis suggest that the Sakrand clay is probably derived from the Tertiary Fossiliferous Limestone formation of the hill ranges lying to the west and consisting mainly of limestone and dolomite with subordinate amount of shale.

The author takes this opportunity to offer his sincere thanks to Dr. S. R. Sen Gupta, Principal, Bengal Engineering College, for his kind interest in the work.